

IMPROVING NATIONAL TOURISM STRATEGY IN UZBEKISTAN.

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Abstract: The article talks about the strategy of tourism development in Uzbekistan and ways to increase its competitiveness.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada O'zbekistonda turizmni rivojlantirish strategiyasi va uning raqobatbardoshligini oshirish yo'llari haqida so'z boradi.

Аннотация: В статье говорится о стратегии развития туризма в Узбекистане и путях повышения его конкурентоспособности.

A national tourism strategy is a government policy that promotes tourism that benefits the country. Many countries have national development strategies related to aspects of their economic or social development; for example, China has had five-year plans since 1953 that set goals and set initiatives to achieve those goals. At the time of writing, China is currently implementing the Thirteenth Five-Year Plan (2016-2020), which includes economic, national defense and even demographic changes.

Many low-income countries have adopted national tourism plans. Tourism is seen as a profitable industry to focus on for several reasons, including:

1. It is one of the largest industries in the world, accounting for 10% of global GDP, 7% of global trade and 10% of global employment (YuVTO, 2017) (see figure below).
2. It can start with a relatively low investment by involving small groups of researchers and gradually increasing the infrastructure over time.
3. Tourism can operate at different scales.
4. Sustainable tourism helps maintain the economic, social and environmental "identity" of a country, especially when compared to other industries such as steel production.

Uzbekistan has great opportunities for the development of the tourism industry. As a result of reform and economic expansion as one of the focus areas, tourism in the country has increased fivefold in the last three years. In

2016, about 1 million tourists visited Uzbekistan, this figure reached 2.7 million in 2017, and in 2018, the number of foreign tourists is expected to reach 7 from more than 5.3 million. By 2025, the annual foreign exchange income from millions of foreign visitors will reach \$2 billion. However, Uzbekistan's tourism sector is still facing problems. These include poor transportation and payment systems, adequate hotels, medical services, language assistance, and lack of information for tourists. Uzbekistan can increase its tourism potential

strengthening cooperation with other countries and international organizations. In addition, Uzbekistan should study its cultural and natural attractions and invest in advertising to increase awareness of these sites. Uzbekistan should also properly use its tourism resources to improve the construction of infrastructure, as well as to attract the development of entrepreneurship and other private sector to the realization of the country's tourism potential.

Tourism is another area of reforms in Uzbekistan:

Tourism is one of the sectors that Uzbekistan seeks to reform and revive since 2019. The reform process is aimed at creating jobs and new business opportunities;

Further expansion of diversification and rapid development of regions;

Increasing incomes and living standards and quality of life, increasing foreign exchange earnings;

Improving the general image and investment of Uzbekistan;

On November 19-21, 2018, Uzbekistan held the first International Investment Forum with the aim of expanding international participation in the field and spreading information about the country's tourism potential;

Reducing barriers:

Promote English (and increasingly Chinese) in the country so that it is easier for international visitors to travel. Reduce visa requirements. A visa is a permit that allows people to enter countries. Many countries require visitors to have a visa because the visitor has to pay for it and it is a way for countries to generate foreign income. (For example, visitors to Egypt usually pay their visa fees in US dollars, British pounds or euros). However, many countries are waiving their visa requirements because they want to encourage people to come to the country and visas are a hindrance. Improve secondary tourism facilities, including upgrading airports, railways and roads.

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